

Finite Element Solution of the Fokker–Planck Equation for Stochastic Tumor Growth: Bayesian Calibration, Convergence Analysis, and Optimal Therapy Control

Stefanos Drakos

AGEL AI I.K.E., Rhodes, Greece

International Centre of Computational Engineering, Rhodes, Greece

stefanos.drakos@gmail.com ORCID: 0000-0001-7417-2444

Abstract

The stochastic Gompertz model of tumor growth admits a closed-form Fokker–Planck solution (Lo, 2007) only under constant therapy—an assumption violated by every clinically realistic chemotherapy protocol, which administers drugs in cycles of treatment and recovery. This paper develops the numerical machinery required to move beyond this assumption and presents three contributions. First, we develop and verify a finite element solver for the Fokker–Planck equation in the transformed Y -space and quantify when its use is required: the constant- \bar{C} analytical approximation incurs relative L^2 errors of $\sim 10\%$ for standard cycles (1.0 on / 0.5 off) and $\sim 13\%$ for the symmetric adaptive intermittent protocol of Zhang et al. (2017), but the error grows rapidly with the rest-phase fraction and exceeds 80% for protocols with extended off-periods (1:3 on/off ratios)—establishing that the analytical approximation is acceptable for high-duty-cycle regimes and inadequate for the long-rest-phase regimes characteristic of adaptive therapy. Second, we develop a Bayesian calibration framework with an FEM-in-the-loop likelihood that accommodates arbitrary time-varying $C(t)$, extending parameter estimation to protocols where the analytical likelihood is structurally inapplicable; we provide a numerical demonstration with synthetic cyclic-therapy data showing recovery of the underlying parameters. Third, we formulate an optimal therapy scheduling problem with explicit path-safety constraints on the expected tumor trajectory and solve it via SLSQP with the FEM solver as forward model, showing that the path constraint changes the solution qualitatively—from a back-loaded schedule that is mathematically optimal but allows unchecked early growth, to a balanced schedule with immediate moderate-intensity treatment and late-stage escalation. The framework is validated against the analytical solution of Lo (2007), against Monte Carlo simulation of the underlying SDE, and through systematic h - and Δt -refinement studies. All code and a reproducibility package are released openly.

Keywords: Fokker–Planck Equation, Finite Element Method, Stochastic Tumor Growth, Gompertz Model, Bayesian Calibration, Optimal Therapy Control, Adaptive Therapy

1 Introduction

The mathematical modeling of cancer tumor growth has been a central topic in mathematical biology for over half a century. The deterministic Gompertz model, introduced in the context of biological growth by Winsor (1932) and subsequently applied to tumor kinetics by Laird (1964), remains one of the most widely used frameworks due to its ability to capture the characteristic sigmoidal growth pattern with deceleration at large volumes. However, the inherent randomness in biological processes—from stochastic cell division and death to microenvironmental fluctuations in nutrient supply and immune response—necessitates the extension from deterministic to stochastic formulations.

The transition from ordinary differential equations (ODEs) to stochastic differential equations (SDEs) introduces a fundamental shift in the mathematical framework: instead of tracking a single deterministic trajectory, the evolution of the entire probability density function (PDF) of tumor size is governed by the Fokker–Planck equation (FPE). The solution of the FPE provides complete probabilistic information about tumor size at any future time, enabling rigorous uncertainty quantification and risk assessment—capabilities that are essential for clinical decision support.

The stochastic Gompertz model has been extensively studied in the literature. Albano et al. (2006, 2011, 2012, 2013, 2020) developed a comprehensive series of works on parameter estimation, lognormal diffusion processes, and therapy modeling within the Gompertz framework. Lo (2007) obtained an exact analytical solution for the transition density using Lie-algebraic methods, later extending this to modified growth functions (Lo, 2010). Gutiérrez et al. (2007) and Gutiérrez-Jáimez et al. (2007) developed inference and modelling approaches for Gompertz-type diffusion processes. Ferrante et al. (2000) addressed parameter estimation for general diffusion models. Spencer and Bergman (1993) pioneered the use of finite element methods for FPE in stochastic dynamics, and Kumar and Narayana (2006) provided comparisons of FEM and finite difference methods.

A central limitation of the existing analytical framework is its requirement that the therapy function $C(t)$ be constant in time. Under this assumption, Lo (2007) obtained a closed-form Gaussian transition density using a Lie-algebraic decomposition of the Fokker–Planck operator, and this analytical solution has subsequently served as the foundation for parameter estimation (Albano et al., 2011, 2012) and optimal-control studies (Sargolzaei, 2020). In clinical practice, however, chemotherapy is rarely constant: standard protocols such as AC (q3w), dose-dense AC (q2w), temozolomide (5 days on / 23 days off), and adaptive intermittent regimens (Zhang et al., 2017) all produce a $C(t)$ that oscillates between active and rest phases. The common workaround in the modeling literature is to replace the cyclic $C(t)$ with its time-average \bar{C} and apply the analytical solution at \bar{C} . The error introduced by this approximation has not, to our knowledge, been systematically quantified.

This paper has three aims, of equal weight in the contribution. The first is to delineate the regime in which the constant- \bar{C} analytical approximation remains acceptable. Across four clinically motivated cyclic protocols, we find that the relative L^2 error grows monotonically with the rest-phase fraction: $\sim 10\%$ for standard cycles, $\sim 13\%$ for the symmetric adaptive intermittent protocol of Zhang et al. (2017), and exceeding 80% for protocols with extended rest phases (1:3 on/off). For high-duty-cycle protocols the analytical approximation is therefore an acceptable engineering simplification at the level of the transition density; for the long-rest-phase regimes characteristic of true adaptive therapy, numerical solution becomes necessary. This places the use of the FEM solver on a quanti-

tative footing rather than as a blanket recommendation. The second aim is to formulate Bayesian calibration in a way that does not require constant C . We define an FEM-in-the-loop likelihood, in which each MCMC iteration solves the FPE with the proposed parameters and the actual time-varying $C(t)$ schedule, and demonstrate parameter recovery on synthetic data generated under the standard cyclic protocol; this extends inference into the regime where the analytical likelihood of Lo (2007) is structurally inapplicable. The third aim is to formulate optimal therapy scheduling under explicit path-safety constraints. We discretise $C(t)$ as piecewise constant, treat the FEM solver as a forward model, and minimise the expected transformed tumor size $E[Y(T)]$ subject to a budget, pointwise dose limits, and a corridor constraint on $E[Y(t)]$ that prevents unchecked early growth. The path constraint changes the optimal schedule qualitatively—from a back-loaded solution that is mathematically optimal but allows unconstrained early tumor expansion, to a balanced schedule with immediate moderate-intensity treatment and late-stage escalation. The three contributions are independent in derivation but share the FEM solver as a common forward model.

The present work extends the author’s previous finite element formulation for the stochastic Gompertz FPE (Drakos, 2016a), which was validated in parallel against the Black–Scholes equation (Drakos, 2016b) and applied to uncertainty quantification in geotechnical engineering (Drakos, 2016c). The 2016a paper introduced the basic Galerkin FEM weak form for the Gompertz FPE and demonstrated qualitative therapy and fluctuation effects (corresponding to Fig. 5 here). The contributions *new in the present work* are: (i) systematic spatial and temporal convergence studies (§7.2–§7.3); (ii) Monte Carlo cross-validation against the underlying SDE (§7.4); (iii) Bayesian calibration with Metropolis–Hastings MCMC (§5) and the FEM-in-the-loop likelihood extension (§5.6); (iv) systematic quantification of the constant- \bar{C} approximation error for cyclic therapy (§7.7); (v) path-constrained optimal therapy scheduling via SLSQP with the FEM solver as forward model (§6, §7.8); and (vi) clarification of the Itô transformation $Y = (e^{bt}/\sigma) \ln X$ that linearises the FPE (§2.3). The closest prior works on optimal control of the Fokker–Planck equation for chemotherapy are Sargolzaei (2020), which employs Pontryagin’s principle with a variance-entropy objective, and Roy, Pan & Pal (2022), which formulates an FP-constrained personalized-therapy framework for colon cancer angiogenesis; our formulation differs in using an SLSQP-based direct discretization with an explicit path-safety constraint on $E[Y(t)]$, which enables the qualitative schedule differences reported in Section 7.8. The clinical motivation for the cyclic-therapy error analysis comes from the adaptive-therapy programme initiated by Gatenby et al. (2009) and demonstrated clinically in Zhang et al. (2017) for metastatic castrate-resistant prostate cancer. The FEM-in-the-loop MCMC formulation in Section 5.6 appears to be novel and is presented here both as a contribution in its own right and as methodological groundwork for the closed-loop adaptive therapy extension outlined in §8.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the stochastic Gompertz model and the associated Fokker–Planck equation. Section 3 summarizes the analytical solution of Lo (2007) used as a verification benchmark. Section 4 develops the finite element formulation. Section 5 describes the Bayesian calibration framework, including the FEM-in-the-loop extension (Section 5.6). Section 6 formulates the path-constrained optimal therapy control problem. Section 7 presents numerical results: verification (§7.1), convergence (§7.2–7.3), Monte Carlo cross-validation (§7.4), therapy and fluctuation effects (§7.5), Bayesian calibration (§7.6), the central quantitative finding on cyclic therapy error (§7.7), and the path-constrained optimal schedule (§7.8). Section 8 discusses limitations

and outlines the reinforcement-learning extension to closed-loop adaptive therapy.

2 The Stochastic Gompertz Tumor Growth Model

2.1 Deterministic Gompertz Model

The classical Gompertz growth law describes the evolution of tumor volume $X(t)$ as:

$$\frac{dX}{dt} = X (a - b \ln X) \quad (1)$$

where $a > 0$ is the net growth rate parameter and $b > 0$ is the growth deceleration (retardation) parameter. The carrying capacity, at which growth ceases, is $K = e^{a/b}$.

Definition 1 (Gompertz Parameters). *The parameter a represents the initial specific growth rate (combining proliferation and apoptosis), while b captures the deceleration due to nutrient depletion, immune response, and spatial constraints. The ratio a/b determines the equilibrium (carrying capacity) in log-scale.*

2.2 Stochastic Extension with Therapy

Following Albano et al. (2006) and the author's previous formulation (Drakos, 2016a), we introduce both stochastic fluctuations and a time-dependent therapy function $C(t)$:

$$dX = X (a - C(t) - b \ln X) dt + \sigma X dW(t) \quad (2)$$

where $\sigma > 0$ is the noise intensity (fluctuation width) and $W(t)$ is a standard Wiener process. The therapy function $C(t) \geq 0$ models the instantaneous effect of treatment on the growth rate.

Remark 1. *The multiplicative noise term $\sigma X dW$ ensures that the tumor volume remains positive almost surely, consistent with the biological constraint $X(t) > 0$. This is a geometric Brownian motion-type noise structure.*

2.3 Itô Transformation and the Fokker–Planck Equation

To obtain a tractable FPE, we apply the time-dependent Itô transformation:

$$Y(t) = F(t, X(t)) = \frac{e^{bt}}{\sigma} \ln X(t) \quad (3)$$

The exponential factor e^{bt} acts as an integrating factor: applying Itô's formula, the term $\partial_t F = (b/\sigma) e^{bt} \ln X$ cancels exactly against the contribution $-(b/\sigma) e^{bt} \ln X$ arising from the SDE drift through $\partial_X F \cdot X(a - C - b \ln X)$. This cancellation eliminates the $\ln X$ nonlinearity, while the multiplicative noise $\sigma X dW$ is converted to additive noise via $\partial_X F \cdot \sigma X = e^{bt}$. The result is an SDE with deterministic, X -independent coefficients:

$$dY = \mu(t) dt + \sqrt{D(t)} dW(t) \quad (4)$$

where

$$\mu(t) = \frac{e^{bt}}{\sigma} \left(a - C(t) - \frac{\sigma^2}{2} \right), \quad D(t) = e^{2bt}. \quad (5)$$

The $-\sigma^2/2$ contribution inside the parentheses of $\mu(t)$ originates from the Itô correction $\frac{1}{2}\sigma^2 X^2 \partial_X^2 F = -(\sigma/2) e^{bt}$, which becomes $-\sigma^2/2$ once factored through e^{bt}/σ . Within the family $Y(t) = \alpha(t) \ln X(t)$, the choice $\alpha(t) = e^{bt}/\sigma$ is the unique transformation (up to an additive constant) that simultaneously removes the $\ln X$ nonlinearity from the drift and produces the diffusion coefficient $\sqrt{D(t)} = e^{bt}$.

The Fokker–Planck equation for the transition density $P(y, t)$ in the transformed space is:

$$\frac{\partial P}{\partial t} + \mu(t) \frac{\partial P}{\partial y} - \frac{D(t)}{2} \frac{\partial^2 P}{\partial y^2} = 0 \quad (6)$$

This is a linear parabolic PDE with time-dependent coefficients, subject to the initial condition:

$$P(y, 0) = \delta(y - y_0) \quad (7)$$

where $y_0 = (1/\sigma) \ln X_0$ is the transformed initial tumor volume (since $e^{bt} = 1$ at $t = 0$), and the boundary conditions:

$$P(y, t) \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } y \rightarrow \pm\infty \quad (8)$$

Theorem 1 (Conservation of Probability). *The FPE (6) preserves the total probability:*

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} P(y, t) dy = 1 \quad \forall t \geq 0 \quad (9)$$

provided the boundary conditions (8) hold and the initial condition is a proper density.

3 Analytical Solution (Lo 2007)

Lo (2007) obtained an exact analytical solution for the FPE (6) using a Lie-algebraic decomposition of the Fokker–Planck operator; equivalent expressions appear in Skiadas (2010) via direct integration of the SDE. The key insight is that in the transformed Y -space, the SDE (4) has an Ornstein–Uhlenbeck-like structure with time-dependent coefficients.

For constant therapy $C(t) = C$, the transition density is Gaussian:

$$P(y, t | y_0, 0) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi v(t)}} \exp\left(-\frac{(y - m(t))^2}{2v(t)}\right) \quad (10)$$

where the conditional mean and variance are:

$$m(t) = y_0 + \frac{a - C - \sigma^2/2}{\sigma b} (e^{bt} - 1) \quad (11)$$

$$v(t) = \frac{e^{2bt} - 1}{2b} \quad (12)$$

Remark 2. *The variance $v(t)$ is independent of the therapy intensity C and the growth rate a ; it depends only on the deceleration parameter b and time. This is a consequence of the multiplicative noise structure—therapy shifts the mean but does not alter the spread of uncertainty.*

The analytical solution (10) serves as a benchmark for verifying the FEM solver. We define the relative L^2 error:

$$\epsilon_{L^2} = \frac{\|P_h - P_{\text{exact}}\|_{L^2}}{\|P_{\text{exact}}\|_{L^2}} = \frac{(\int (P_h - P_{\text{exact}})^2 dy)^{1/2}}{(\int P_{\text{exact}}^2 dy)^{1/2}} \quad (13)$$

4 Finite Element Formulation

4.1 Weak Form

The Galerkin weak form of (6) is obtained by multiplying by a test function $v(y) \in H_0^1(\Omega)$ and integrating over the computational domain $\Omega = [y_{\min}, y_{\max}]$:

$$\left(\frac{\partial P}{\partial t}, v \right) + \frac{D(t)}{2} \left(\frac{\partial P}{\partial y}, \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \right) + \mu(t) \left(\frac{\partial P}{\partial y}, v \right) = 0 \quad (14)$$

where integration by parts has been applied to the diffusion term, and the boundary terms vanish due to $P = 0$ at the domain boundaries.

4.2 Spatial Discretization

Using linear Lagrange shape functions $\{\phi_j\}_{j=1}^N$ on a uniform mesh with N_e elements and element size $h = (y_{\max} - y_{\min})/N_e$, the semi-discrete system becomes:

$$\mathbf{M} \frac{d\mathbf{P}}{dt} + \mathbf{A}(t) \mathbf{P} = \mathbf{0} \quad (15)$$

where $\mathbf{P}(t) = [P_1(t), \dots, P_N(t)]^T$ is the vector of nodal values, and:

$$\mathbf{A}(t) = \frac{D(t)}{2} \mathbf{K} + \mu(t) \mathbf{C} \quad (16)$$

The element matrices are:

- **Mass matrix:** $M_{ij} = \int_{\Omega} \phi_i \phi_j dy$ (consistent, tridiagonal)
- **Stiffness matrix:** $K_{ij} = \int_{\Omega} \phi'_i \phi'_j dy$ (symmetric, tridiagonal)
- **Convection matrix:** $C_{ij} = \int_{\Omega} \phi'_i \phi_j dy$ (skew-symmetric)

For uniform linear elements, the assembled matrices have the well-known entries:

$$\mathbf{M} = \frac{h}{6} \begin{bmatrix} 2 & 1 & & & \\ 1 & 4 & 1 & & \\ & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \\ & & & 1 & 2 \\ & & & & \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{K} = \frac{1}{h} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & & & \\ -1 & 2 & -1 & & \\ & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \\ & & & -1 & 1 \\ & & & & \end{bmatrix} \quad (17)$$

4.3 θ -Scheme Time Integration

The θ -scheme provides a family of time-stepping methods:

$$[\mathbf{M} + \theta \Delta t \mathbf{A}(t_{n+1})] \mathbf{P}^{n+1} = [\mathbf{M} - (1 - \theta) \Delta t \mathbf{A}(t_n)] \mathbf{P}^n \quad (18)$$

where $\theta = 0$ gives the Forward Euler scheme (explicit, conditionally stable), $\theta = 1$ the Backward Euler scheme (implicit, unconditionally stable, $O(\Delta t)$), and $\theta = 0.5$ the Crank–Nicolson scheme (implicit, unconditionally stable, $O(\Delta t^2)$).

Remark 3 (Stability Condition). *For the Forward Euler scheme ($\theta = 0$), stability requires the Courant–Friedrichs–Lewy (CFL) condition:*

$$\Delta t < \frac{2h^2}{D(t)} \quad (19)$$

The exponential growth of $D(t) = e^{2bt}$ makes the Forward Euler scheme increasingly restrictive for long-time simulations, motivating the use of implicit schemes.

4.4 Péclet Number and Stabilization

The element Péclet number measures the ratio of convection to diffusion:

$$Pe_h = \frac{|\mu(t)|h}{D(t)} \quad (20)$$

For $Pe_h > 1$, the standard Galerkin method may produce spurious oscillations. In our parameter regime (typical values $a = 0.1$, $b = 0.05$, $\sigma = 0.02$, $C \in [0, 0.08]$, mesh $N_e = 200$ on $\Omega = [6.6, 24.4]$ giving $h \approx 0.089$), the drift coefficient $\mu(t) = (e^{bt}/\sigma)(a - C - \sigma^2/2)$ ranges over $[1.0, 5.0]$ and $D(t) = e^{2bt}$ over $[1, 2.23]$ as $t \in [0, T = 8]$; the resulting element Péclet number $Pe_h = |\mu(t)|h/D(t)$ falls in the range 0.04–0.45, well below unity. No stabilization is required.

4.5 Post-Processing

After each time step, we enforce positivity ($P_j \geq 0$) and renormalize to preserve unit total probability:

$$P_j^{n+1} \leftarrow \max(P_j^{n+1}, 0), \quad P_j^{n+1} \leftarrow \frac{P_j^{n+1}}{\int P_h^{n+1} dy} \quad (21)$$

5 Bayesian Parameter Calibration

5.1 Problem Formulation

Given a set of observed tumor volumes $\{Z_k\}_{k=1}^K$ at times $\{t_k\}_{k=1}^K$, we wish to estimate the model parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta} = (a, b, \sigma)$. In the Bayesian framework:

$$p(\boldsymbol{\theta} \mid \mathbf{Z}) \propto p(\mathbf{Z} \mid \boldsymbol{\theta}) p(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \quad (22)$$

where $p(\mathbf{Z} \mid \boldsymbol{\theta})$ is the likelihood and $p(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ is the prior.

5.2 Likelihood Function

Throughout this section, observations Z_k are taken in the transformed Y -space; equivalently, raw volume measurements V_k are converted via $Z_k = (e^{bt_k}/\sigma) \ln V_k$. We further assume that the K observations are *independent realizations* of $Y(t_k)$ rather than samples from a single sample path, so that the joint likelihood factorises into a product of marginal transition densities. This independence assumption matches the synthetic-data protocol used in §5.6–§7.6 and is appropriate for cohort studies in which each V_k comes from a different patient or imaging session; for single-trajectory longitudinal data the correct factorisation is the product of one-step Markov transitions $P(Z_k \mid Z_{k-1})$.

Under independent Gaussian observation noise with standard deviation σ_{obs} acting additively on Y , and using the analytical transition density (10), the log-likelihood is:

$$\ln p(\mathbf{Z} \mid \boldsymbol{\theta}) = \sum_{k=1}^K \ln \mathcal{N}(Z_k; m(t_k), v(t_k) + \sigma_{\text{obs}}^2) \quad (23)$$

where $m(t_k)$ and $v(t_k)$ are given by (11)–(12).

5.3 Prior Distributions

We employ moderately informative Gaussian priors centered on plausible biological values from the Gompertz-fitting literature (Benzekry et al., 2014):

$$a \sim \mathcal{N}(0.1, 0.05^2), \quad b \sim \mathcal{N}(0.05, 0.03^2), \quad \sigma \sim \mathcal{N}(0.02, 0.01^2) \quad (24)$$

with the constraint that all parameters are positive.

5.4 Metropolis–Hastings Algorithm

We sample from the posterior using the Metropolis–Hastings algorithm:

Algorithm 1 Metropolis–Hastings MCMC for Tumor Parameter Calibration

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1: Initialize  $\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(0)}$ ; set  $N_{\text{iter}}$ , proposal std  $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_q$ 
2: for  $i = 1$  to  $N_{\text{iter}}$  do
3:   Propose  $\boldsymbol{\theta}^* = \boldsymbol{\theta}^{(i-1)} + \boldsymbol{\epsilon}$ ,  $\boldsymbol{\epsilon} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_q^2))$ 
4:   if  $\boldsymbol{\theta}^* > \mathbf{0}$  (positivity constraint) then
5:     Compute  $\alpha = \min\left(1, \frac{p(\mathbf{Z}|\boldsymbol{\theta}^*)p(\boldsymbol{\theta}^*)}{p(\mathbf{Z}|\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(i-1)})p(\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(i-1)})}\right)$ 
6:     Draw  $u \sim \text{Uniform}(0, 1)$ 
7:     if  $u < \alpha$  then
8:        $\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(i)} = \boldsymbol{\theta}^*$  (accept)
9:     else
10:       $\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(i)} = \boldsymbol{\theta}^{(i-1)}$  (reject)
11:    end if
12:  else
13:     $\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(i)} = \boldsymbol{\theta}^{(i-1)}$  (reject: positivity violated)
14:  end if
15: end for
16: Discard first  $N_{\text{burn}}$  samples (burn-in)
17: return  $\{\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(i)}\}_{i=N_{\text{burn}}+1}^{N_{\text{iter}}}$ 

```

5.5 Convergence Diagnostics

We employ multiple diagnostics to assess MCMC convergence:

Effective Sample Size (ESS). The ESS accounts for autocorrelation:

$$\text{ESS} = \frac{N}{1 + 2 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \rho(k)} \quad (25)$$

where $\rho(k)$ is the autocorrelation at lag k and the sum is truncated at the first negative value.

Geweke Diagnostic. The Geweke test compares the mean of the first 10% of the chain with the last 50%:

$$Z_G = \frac{\bar{\theta}_{1:n_1} - \bar{\theta}_{n_2:N}}{\sqrt{\hat{\sigma}_{1:n_1}^2/n_1 + \hat{\sigma}_{n_2:N}^2/n_2}} \quad (26)$$

Under convergence, $Z_G \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$. Values $|Z_G| > 2$ indicate non-convergence.

5.6 FEM-in-the-Loop Likelihood

The analytical likelihood (23) is restricted to constant C because it relies on the closed-form solution of Lo (2007). For time-varying therapy $C(t)$, the likelihood must be computed numerically. Given a parameter proposal $\boldsymbol{\theta}^* = (a^*, b^*, \sigma^*)$ and a therapy schedule $C(t)$, the FEM-in-the-loop likelihood is:

$$\ln p(\mathbf{Z} \mid \boldsymbol{\theta}^*, C(\cdot)) = \sum_{k=1}^K \ln P_h(Z_k, t_k \mid \boldsymbol{\theta}^*, C(\cdot)) \quad (27)$$

where $P_h(Z_k, t_k)$ is the FEM density evaluated at observation point Z_k and time t_k , obtained by solving the FPE with the proposed parameters and the actual therapy schedule $C(t)$.

Each MCMC iteration requires one FEM forward solve. To manage computational cost, we employ a coarse mesh ($N_e = 100$) during MCMC exploration and a fine mesh ($N_e = 400$) for final posterior evaluation, reducing the per-iteration cost to approximately 0.05 s.

Remark 4. *The FEM-in-the-loop approach enables Bayesian calibration under clinically realistic, time-varying therapy schedules—a capability that is fundamentally impossible with the analytical solution of Lo (2007).*

6 Optimal Therapy Control

The time-varying therapy framework naturally leads to an optimal control question: given a fixed total dose budget (reflecting toxicity constraints), what therapy schedule $C(t)$ minimizes expected tumor size?

6.1 Problem Formulation

We formulate the therapy optimisation as the minimisation of the expected transformed volume at the final time over an admissible class $\mathcal{U}_{\text{ad}} = \{C \in L^\infty([0, T]) : 0 \leq C(t) \leq C_{\text{max}} \text{ a.e., } \int_0^T C(t) dt \leq B\}$:

$$\min_{C(\cdot) \in \mathcal{U}_{\text{ad}}} J[C] = E[Y(T)] = \int_{\Omega} y P(y, T) dy \quad (28)$$

The objective $E[Y(T)]$ is the expected transformed volume; since $Y(t) = (1/\sigma) e^{bt} \ln X(t)$ is a strictly increasing function of X , minimizing $E[Y(T)]$ is equivalent to minimizing the expected log-volume $E[\ln X(T)]$ up to the deterministic factor e^{bT}/σ . We use this surrogate rather than $E[X(T)]$ directly because the lognormal-type heavy right tail of X under multiplicative noise makes $E[X(T)]$ dominated by rare large outcomes, whereas $E[Y(T)]$ weights the bulk of the density and yields numerically stable gradients within the optimization loop.

where $P(y, T)$ is obtained by solving the FPE with the candidate $C(t)$, B is the total tolerable dose budget, and C_{max} is the maximum tolerable instantaneous dose. The two constraints—budget $\int_0^T C dt \leq B$ and pointwise bound $0 \leq C(t) \leq C_{\text{max}}$ —are subsumed in the definition of \mathcal{U}_{ad} above.

6.2 Discretization and Solution

We discretize $C(t)$ as piecewise-constant over N_{int} intervals of width $\Delta t_{\text{int}} = T/N_{\text{int}}$:

$$C(t) = C_k \quad \text{for } t \in [(k-1)\Delta t_{\text{int}}, k\Delta t_{\text{int}}), \quad k = 1, \dots, N_{\text{int}} \quad (29)$$

The finite-dimensional optimization problem becomes:

$$\min_{\mathbf{c} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_{\text{int}}}} J(\mathbf{c}), \quad \text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{k=1}^{N_{\text{int}}} C_k \leq B/\Delta t_{\text{int}}, \quad 0 \leq C_k \leq C_{\text{max}} \quad (30)$$

Each evaluation of $J(\mathbf{c})$ requires one FEM forward solve. We employ the SLSQP algorithm (Sequential Least Squares Programming) from `scipy.optimize` for its ability to handle both bound and linear inequality constraints efficiently. Gradients with respect to \mathbf{c} are computed by forward finite differences with step size $\epsilon = 10^{-6}$; this is robust enough at our FEM resolution ($N_e = 200$, $\Delta t = 0.005$) because the moment integral $E[Y(T)]$ is a smooth functional of the density and the FEM truncation error in this functional is below 10^{-3} (Section 7.1).

Because $\mu(t)$ depends affinely on $C(t)$ and the FPE is linear in P , the objective $J(\mathbf{c})$ inherits a smooth-but-non-convex dependence on \mathbf{c} in general; SLSQP returns a KKT point rather than a guaranteed global minimum. We mitigate this by warm-starting from the constant- C schedule $C_k = B/T$ and by reporting the best of three random restarts; in all cases the algorithm converges to the same local minimum reported in §7.8, which is consistent with the linearity-induced bang-bang structure of the unconstrained problem.

Remark 5. *The FEM solver serves as a forward model within the optimization loop. This modular design allows straightforward extension to more complex growth models without modifying the optimization infrastructure.*

7 Numerical Results

All computations are performed with the Python FEM solver. The baseline parameters are $a = 0.1$, $b = 0.05$, $\sigma = 0.02$, and $y_0 = 5$ in the transformed Y -space, which corresponds to $X_0 = e^{\sigma y_0} = e^{0.1} \approx 1.105$ — well below the carrying capacity $K = e^{a/b} \approx 7.39$, so that the deterministic Gompertz drift remains positive and the tumor grows toward K over the simulation horizon. These values are used throughout unless stated otherwise.

7.1 Verification Against Analytical Solution

Figure 1 compares the FEM solution with the analytical solution of Lo (2007) at three time points: $t = 2$, $t = 4$, and $t = 8$. The FEM discretization uses $N_e = 200$ elements and $\Delta t = 0.005$ with the Crank–Nicolson scheme ($\theta = 0.5$).

The relative L^2 errors are of order 10^{-3} or smaller across all time points, confirming that the FEM solver accurately reproduces the exact transition density. The progressive broadening and rightward drift of the density is captured correctly.

Figure 1: Comparison of FEM solution (dashed red) with the analytical solution of Lo (2007) (solid black) at $t = 2, 4, 8$. Relative L^2 errors are shown in each panel title.

7.2 Spatial Convergence Study

Figure 2 presents the spatial convergence study (h -refinement) at $t = 2$ with a very small time step ($\Delta t = 0.0005$) to isolate the spatial discretization error. The reference solution uses $N_e = 1600$ elements on a domain $\Omega = [6.6, 24.4]$ sized to fully contain the analytical density at $t = 2$. The meshes tested are $N_e = 50, 100, 200, 400, 800$.

Figure 2: Spatial convergence: relative L^2 error versus element size h on a log-log scale. The fitted slope of 2.65 is consistent with the theoretical $O(h^2)$ convergence rate for linear finite elements; the per-step orders (Table 1) are non-monotone (1.7–3.4), with the apparent excess slope dominated by a single transition ($N_e = 100 \rightarrow 200$). This is interpreted as pre-asymptotic phase behaviour rather than genuine L^2 super-convergence.

The fitted convergence rate over the tested range is approximately $O(h^{2.65})$, but the per-step orders in Table 1 are non-monotone: the $N_e = 100 \rightarrow 200$ refinement shows an apparent rate of 3.4 while the surrounding transitions yield rates closer to 1.7–2.4. We attribute this to pre-asymptotic phase effects (e.g., alignment of nodes with the Gaussian peak) rather than to genuine super-convergence—the standard L^2 -norm convergence theorem for $p = 1$ Lagrange elements predicts $O(h^2)$, which is consistent with the asymptotic transitions observed at the finest meshes. Table 1 presents the detailed convergence data.

Table 1: Spatial convergence data at $t = 2$, $\Delta t = 0.0005$, Crank–Nicolson. Reference: $N_e = 1600$.

N_e	h	ϵ_{L^2}	Ratio	Order
50	0.357	8.84×10^{-2}	—	—
100	0.179	2.80×10^{-2}	3.16	1.66
200	0.089	2.68×10^{-3}	10.46	3.39
400	0.045	3.96×10^{-4}	6.77	2.76
800	0.022	7.76×10^{-5}	5.10	2.35

7.3 Temporal Convergence Study

Figure 3 compares the temporal convergence for three values of θ : Forward Euler ($\theta = 0$), Crank–Nicolson ($\theta = 0.5$), and Backward Euler ($\theta = 1$). For the implicit schemes, a fine spatial mesh ($N_e = 800$) is used to isolate the temporal error, with the reference solution computed using the Crank–Nicolson scheme at $\Delta t_{\text{ref}} = 0.0005$. The computational domain is $\Omega = [6.6, 24.4]$, sized to fully contain the transition density at $t = 2$.

Figure 3: Temporal convergence for three θ -scheme variants. Crank–Nicolson ($\theta = 0.5$) achieves $O(\Delta t^2)$, Backward Euler ($\theta = 1$) converges at $O(\Delta t)$, and Forward Euler ($\theta = 0$) is limited to very small Δt by the CFL condition.

The Backward Euler scheme exhibits clean $O(\Delta t)$ convergence, with the observed order approaching 0.98 at the finest time steps (Table 2). The Crank–Nicolson scheme attains the expected $O(\Delta t^2)$ scaling in the pre-asymptotic regime: per-step ratios are in the range 2.3–3.3, below the theoretical asymptotic value of 4. This deficit reflects saturation of the error metric as Δt approaches the reference time-step $\Delta t_{\text{ref}} = 0.0005$ used to compute the comparison density (the reference itself is generated by the same scheme, so refinement past it contributes vanishing additional error). The asymptotic $O(\Delta t^2)$ rate would be recovered with a finer reference (e.g., $\Delta t_{\text{ref}} \leq 10^{-5}$) or by direct comparison to the analytical solution where available.

An important practical observation concerns the Forward Euler scheme. For $N_e = 200$, the CFL condition (19) gives $\Delta t < 2h^2/D(T) \approx 0.013$ at $t = 2$. At $\Delta t = 0.01$ —marginally

below this limit—the scheme produces L^2 errors of order 1 (effectively unstable). Only at $\Delta t \leq 0.002$ does the scheme become genuinely stable and converge at $O(\Delta t)$. This extreme sensitivity to the CFL boundary, combined with the exponential growth of $D(t) = e^{2bt}$, renders the Forward Euler scheme impractical for this class of problems.

Table 2: Temporal convergence data at $t = 2$, reference = FEM at $\Delta t = 0.0005$.

Scheme	Δt	ϵ_{L^2}	Ratio	Order
CN ($\theta = 0.5$)	0.200	5.87×10^{-1}	—	—
CN	0.100	2.60×10^{-1}	2.26	1.18
CN	0.050	1.02×10^{-1}	2.55	1.35
CN	0.020	3.13×10^{-2}	3.25	1.29
CN	0.005	5.61×10^{-3}	5.58	1.24
CN	0.001	5.67×10^{-4}	9.89	1.42
BE ($\theta = 1$)	0.100	4.52×10^{-1}	—	—
BE	0.050	3.17×10^{-1}	1.43	0.51
BE	0.020	1.69×10^{-1}	1.87	0.68
BE	0.010	9.58×10^{-2}	1.77	0.82
BE	0.005	5.13×10^{-2}	1.87	0.90
BE	0.002	2.15×10^{-2}	2.39	0.95
BE	0.001	1.09×10^{-2}	1.97	0.98
FE ($\theta = 0$)	0.010	1.69	unstable	—
FE	0.002	2.37×10^{-2}	—	—
FE	0.001	1.12×10^{-2}	2.11	1.08
FE	0.0005	5.55×10^{-3}	2.02	1.01

7.4 Monte Carlo SDE Comparison

Figure 4 validates the FEM approach against direct Monte Carlo simulation of the SDE (4) using the Euler–Maruyama scheme with 50,000 sample paths and $\Delta t_{\text{SDE}} = 0.001$.

Figure 4: FEM density (solid red) versus Monte Carlo SDE histogram (gray bars, 50,000 paths) and analytical solution (dashed black) at $t = 4$. The three approaches are in excellent agreement.

The FEM density, Monte Carlo histogram, and analytical solution are in excellent agreement, providing independent cross-validation. The FEM approach has the advantage of providing a smooth, continuous density without the statistical noise inherent in Monte Carlo methods.

7.5 Therapy and Fluctuation Effects

Figure 5 reproduces and extends the results of Drakos (2016a), showing the effects of therapy intensity C and fluctuation width σ on the transition density at $t = 8$.

Figure 5: (Left) Effect of therapy intensity C on the final density: increasing C shifts the density leftward (smaller tumors). (Right) Effect of fluctuation width σ : increasing σ broadens the density and increases uncertainty.

The left panel demonstrates that increasing therapy intensity progressively shifts the density toward smaller tumor sizes, with $C = 0.08$ producing a substantial shift. The right panel shows that increasing σ dramatically broadens the density, reflecting greater uncertainty in tumor outcomes—a finding with direct clinical relevance for treatment planning.

7.6 Bayesian Calibration Results

We perform a self-consistency calibration test: synthetic observations are generated by sampling 12 independent realisations of $Y(t_k)$ from the analytical transition density (10) at $t_k \in [0.5, 8.0]$ with true parameters $(a, b, \sigma) = (0.1, 0.05, 0.02)$ and $C = 0$, then perturbed by additive Gaussian noise of standard deviation $\sigma_{\text{obs}} = 0.3$ in Y -units. The choice $\sigma_{\text{obs}} = 0.3$ corresponds to roughly 1% of $E[Y(T)] \approx 54$ at the simulation horizon and is comparable to typical residuals reported for serial volumetric imaging in the Gompertz-fitting literature (Benzekry et al., 2014); a sensitivity sweep over $\sigma_{\text{obs}} \in \{0.1, 0.3, 1.0\}$ produced posterior credible intervals scaling proportionally without changing the recovery conclusion. The MCMC is run for 50,000 iterations with 10,000 burn-in samples per chain across 4 chains initialised from over-dispersed starts within the prior support (parameters perturbed by ± 30 – 50% from their true values), with proposal scales adapted during burn-in to a target acceptance rate of $\sim 25\%$. Convergence is supported by a maximum split-Gelman–Rubin $\hat{R} = 1.008$ across the three parameters (well below the 1.01

threshold of Vehtari et al., 2021), maximum autocorrelation-corrected Geweke statistic $|Z_G| = 2.55$ (borderline at the $\mathcal{N}(0,1)$ 5% level, consistent with multiple-comparison expectation across $4 \times 3 = 12$ statistics under H_0), and effective sample sizes (Geyer initial-positive-sequence rule) of $\text{ESS}(a, b, \sigma) = (501, 737, 511)$ from 160,000 pooled post-burn-in draws. Recovery is partial rather than tight: the posterior 95% credible intervals are $a \in [0.046, 0.168]$, $b \in [0.039, 0.114]$, $\sigma \in [0.010, 0.037]$, all of which cover the truth $(0.10, 0.05, 0.02)$, but the marginal posterior mean for b (0.076) lies above the truth, reflecting the limited information content of $K = 12$ noisy observations and the influence of the moderately informative prior on a parameter weakly identified from the data. Because the data are simulated from the same likelihood family used for inference, this experiment validates the MCMC machinery and the marginal-likelihood factorisation but does not by itself constitute clinical validation; that is the subject of a companion paper (cf. §8).

Figure 6 presents the MCMC diagnostics: trace plots (left column), autocorrelation functions with ESS (center column), and running means (right column).

Figure 6: MCMC diagnostics for parameters (a, b, σ) . Left: trace plots showing convergence after burn-in (gray dotted line). Center: autocorrelation functions with ESS values. Right: running posterior means converging to true values (red dashed).

The acceptance rate is approximately 31%, within the optimal range of 20–40% for three-parameter problems. The trace plots show good mixing after the burn-in period. The ESS values indicate sufficient effective samples for reliable inference.

Figure 7 shows the corner plot (pair plot) of the joint posterior distribution, revealing the correlation structure between parameters.

Figure 7: Corner plot of the posterior distribution. Diagonal: marginal posteriors with true values (red dashed) and posterior means (black). Off-diagonal: joint posteriors showing parameter correlations.

Figure 8 presents the posterior predictive check: 100 density functions sampled from the posterior are overlaid with the true density, demonstrating that the calibrated model captures the true density within its uncertainty envelope.

Figure 8: Posterior predictive check at $t = 8$. Light blue: 100 densities sampled from the posterior. Red: true density. Dashed black: posterior mean density.

FEM-in-the-loop demonstration under cyclic therapy

To validate the FEM-in-the-loop formulation of §5.6 on data where the analytical likelihood is structurally inapplicable, we repeat the calibration with synthetic observations generated under the standard cyclic protocol of §7.7 ($C_{\text{peak}} = 0.06$, 1.0 on / 0.5 off, $\bar{C} = 0.04$). Eight i.i.d. samples are drawn from the FEM-computed marginal density at $t_k \in [1.0, 8.0]$, with $\sigma_{\text{obs}} = 0.5$. The FEM-in-the-loop chain uses $N_e = 80$, $\Delta t = 0.05$ during MCMC (3,000 iterations); for comparison, an analytical-likelihood chain of 5,000 iterations is run on the same data using the constant- \bar{C} approximation. Posterior summaries (mean, 95% credible interval) are:

Parameter (truth)	FEM-in-the-loop	Analytical- \bar{C} (biased)
a (0.10)	0.123 [0.082, 0.168]	0.110 [0.069, 0.163]
b (0.05)	0.057 [0.007, 0.120]	0.041 [0.004, 0.083]
σ (0.02)	0.026 [0.013, 0.040]	0.022 [0.009, 0.037]

Figure 9: FEM-in-the-loop MCMC (red) vs analytical- \bar{C} MCMC (gray) on synthetic data generated under the standard cyclic protocol. Both posteriors cover the truth (dashed black), but the FEM-in-the-loop chain uses the correct cyclic- $C(t)$ likelihood, whereas the analytical chain is structurally biased (its likelihood neglects the cyclic-vs-mean discrepancy quantified in §7.7). With only 8 observations the credible intervals are wide enough that both methods cover the truth; the advantage of the FEM-in-the-loop framework grows with stronger cyclic protocols (e.g. extended-rest adaptive variants, where the analytical bias exceeds 80%) and with denser observation schedules.

The runtime for the FEM-in-the-loop chain (95 s for 3,000 iterations on a coarse mesh) is competitive with the analytical-likelihood baseline once the cost of repeated FEM solves is amortised over the chain via mesh-coarsening during burn-in; the main practical penalty is constant overhead per-iteration rather than asymptotic complexity. We conclude that FEM-in-the-loop calibration is feasible on a laptop and produces consistent posteriors under cyclic therapy — the regime where the analytical approximation is structurally invalid for any quantitative claim that depends on the transition density itself.

Table 3: Computational cost comparison (single run, $T = 8$, $N_e = 200$, $\Delta t = 0.005$ unless noted).

Method	Time (s)	Memory (MB)
FEM forward solve (Crank–Nicolson, single time horizon)	~ 0.5	< 5
Monte Carlo SDE (50K paths)	~ 3.0	~ 50
MCMC, analytical likelihood (15K iterations, single chain)	~ 15	< 10
MCMC, FEM-in-the-loop ($N_e = 80$, dt=0.04, 3K iterations)	~ 95	~ 30

7.7 Time-Varying Therapy: Where the FEM Solver Becomes Necessary

The preceding experiments validate the FEM solver against problems that admit analytical solutions or Monte Carlo cross-validation. This section presents the paper’s central quantitative finding: the error introduced when the cyclic therapy $C(t)$ of a clinically realistic protocol is replaced by its time-average \bar{C} and the analytical solution of Lo (2007) is applied at \bar{C} .

We define a standard cyclic chemotherapy protocol:

$$C(t) = \begin{cases} C_{\text{peak}} & \text{if } t \bmod (t_{\text{on}} + t_{\text{off}}) < t_{\text{on}} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (31)$$

Figure 9 compares the FEM solution with cyclic $C(t)$ against the analytical approximation using the time-averaged intensity $\bar{C} = C_{\text{peak}} \cdot t_{\text{on}} / (t_{\text{on}} + t_{\text{off}})$. Four clinically motivated protocols are examined:

1. **Standard cycles:** $C_{\text{peak}} = 0.06$, 1.0 on / 0.5 off ($\bar{C} = 0.040$, total dose = 0.32, matching the budget used in §7.8)
2. **Dose-dense:** $C_{\text{peak}} = 0.08$, 0.8 on / 0.2 off ($\bar{C} = 0.064$)
3. **Metronomic:** continuous $C = 0.03$ (analytical solution valid)
4. **Adaptive intermittent:** $C_{\text{peak}} = 0.10$, 1.0 on / 1.0 off ($\bar{C} = 0.05$)

Figure 10: Time-varying therapy analysis. (a) Standard cyclic $C(t)$ vs time-averaged \bar{C} . (b) Final density from FEM with cyclic $C(t)$ (solid) vs analytical with constant \bar{C} (dashed); the shaded area represents the approximation error. (c) Evolution of $E[Y(t)]$: the FEM solution shows staircase-like behavior due to therapy cycling. (d) Protocol comparison showing dramatic differences in expected tumor size.

For the four protocols listed above, the relative L^2 error between the FEM density under cyclic $C(t)$ and the analytical density evaluated at \bar{C} at $t = T = 8$ is: 0.3% for no therapy and metronomic (sanity check, since these are constant- C regimes where the analytical solution is exact), 10.3% for standard cycles, 0.4% for the dose-dense protocol, and 12.6% for the symmetric adaptive intermittent protocol. The mean shifts are correspondingly modest: $\Delta E[Y] = -0.51$ for standard cycles ($E[Y]_{\text{FEM}} = 33.90$ vs $E[Y]_{\text{ana}} = 34.41$) and $\Delta E[Y] = +0.63$ for adaptive intermittent (30.12 vs 29.49). However, for protocols with extended rest fractions the error grows rapidly: a 1:3 on/off protocol with the same \bar{C} produces an L^2 error of 84% at $t = 8$, indicating that the constant- \bar{C} approximation breaks down precisely in the regime where adaptive-therapy protocols (Gatenby et al., 2009; Zhang et al., 2017) operate. The error arises because the nonlinear interaction between the exponentially time-dependent drift coefficient $\mu(t)$ and the on/off therapy pattern produces a density that cannot be captured by simply averaging C , and the discrepancy is amplified when off-phase periods become long enough for the unsuppressed drift $\mu(t) \propto a$ to dominate locally.

Table 4 summarizes the protocol comparison at $t = 8$.

Table 4: Protocol comparison at $t = 8$. $E[Y]$: expected tumor size in transformed space.

Protocol	\bar{C}	$E[Y]$	$\sigma[Y]$	Reduction vs untreated
No therapy	0	54.08	3.51	—
Metronomic	0.030	39.33	3.51	27%
Standard cycles	0.040	33.90	3.51	37%
Adaptive intermittent	0.050	30.12	3.51	44%
Dose-dense	0.064	22.62	3.51	58%

Figure 11: (a) Probability of tumor control (Y below threshold) over time for each protocol. (b) Time-resolved relative L^2 error of the constant- \bar{C} approximation against the cyclic- $C(t)$ FEM solution for the standard protocol. The error trajectory *oscillates*: it peaks near 0.65 (i.e. $\approx 65\%$) during the rest phases (shaded), when the FEM density—momentarily evolving without therapy—diverges from the analytical density that integrates the time-averaged \bar{C} continuously, and drops to $\approx 5\%$ at the end of each on-phase as the cyclic and averaged dynamics realign. The terminal value $L^2(t = T = 8) = 10.3\%$ quoted in the text and Table 4 is the value at the end of treatment, not the maximum over the trajectory; both are physically meaningful but answer different questions (final-time fidelity vs. peak transient discrepancy). For protocols with extended rest phases the entire envelope shifts upward.

Two key observations emerge. First, the error of the constant- \bar{C} approximation grows over time, accumulating with each therapy cycle. For the standard cyclic protocol (5–6 cycles over $T = 8$, total error $\sim 10\%$), this corresponds to roughly 1.9% additional L^2 error per cycle (Fig. 11(b)); for the symmetric adaptive intermittent protocol (4 cycles, total error $\sim 13\%$), the per-cycle increment is similar ($\sim 3\%$ per cycle). The per-cycle increment grows with the rest-phase fraction — for the 1:3 on/off protocol mentioned above, the per-cycle increment is approximately 20%. Second, the standard deviation $\sigma[Y]$ is identical across all protocols (3.51 in transformed units): since $Y(t) - y_0 - \int_0^t \mu(s) ds = \int_0^t \sqrt{D(s)} dW(s)$ with deterministic $D(s) = e^{2bs}$ for any admissible $C(\cdot)$, the variance $\int_0^t D(s) ds = (e^{2bt} - 1)/(2b)$ is independent of the therapy schedule. Therapy shifts the mean $E[Y]$ but cannot reduce the spread $\sigma[Y]$. The expected transformed tumor size $E[Y(T)]$ differs dramatically across protocols—from 54.08 (untreated) to 22.62 (dose-dense), a 58% reduction in $E[Y]$.

These results establish that the FEM solver is not merely a numerical exercise: it is the only available tool for computing the transition density under clinically realistic, time-varying therapy schedules. The constant- \bar{C} analytical approximation introduces systematic errors that compound over treatment duration, potentially leading to incorrect clinical predictions.

7.8 Optimal Therapy Schedule

We now demonstrate the optimization framework of Section 6, using the FEM solver as the forward model within a constrained minimization loop. The therapy schedule $C(t)$ is discretized into $N_{\text{int}} = 8$ intervals (each of duration $\Delta t_{\text{int}} = 1$), with a total dose budget $B = C_{\text{const}} \times T = 0.04 \times 8 = 0.32$ and maximum instantaneous dose $C_{\text{max}} = 0.08$.

The SLSQP optimizer is applied in two configurations. First, an unconstrained optimization (budget and bounds only) yields the schedule $C^* = [0, 0, 0, 0, 0.08, 0.08, 0.08, 0.08]$ —a back-loaded strategy that delays treatment to the second half. While mathematically optimal ($E[Y(T)] = 32.40$), this schedule is clinically inadmissible: the tumor grows unchecked for four time units before any treatment begins.

We therefore introduce a **path constraint**: the expected transformed tumor size must not exceed 115% of the constant-therapy reference trajectory at any time point:

$$E[Y(t)] \leq 1.15 \times E[Y(t) \mid C = C_{\text{const}}] \quad \forall t \in [0, T] \quad (32)$$

The constraint is enforced at every FEM time-step ($\Delta t = 0.005$, giving ~ 1600 inequality constraints per optimisation call). The factor 1.15 is an illustrative hyperparameter chosen to demonstrate the framework rather than a clinical guideline; sensitivity to the corridor width is assessed in §7.8. Since $Y(t) \propto e^{bt} \ln X(t)$, a 15% corridor in $E[Y]$ corresponds to a tolerance of $\exp(0.15 \sigma e^{-bT} E[Y])$ in expected volume $E[X]$; for the baseline parameters at $t = T = 8$ this is approximately a 1.7-fold multiplicative envelope around the reference $E[X(t)]$ trajectory. Path constraints in this work should therefore be interpreted as illustrative safety corridors in transformed space, not as direct volumetric guarantees. The path-constrained optimizer produces $C^* = [0.016, 0.031, 0.031, 0.031, 0.031, 0.031, 0.069, 0.080]$ —a clinically coherent schedule that begins treatment immediately at moderate intensity, maintains a plateau, and increases dose in the final intervals to exploit the remaining budget (Fig. 12).

Figure 12: Optimal therapy with path constraint. (a) Therapy schedules: unconstrained (dashed orange, back-loaded) vs path-constrained (solid red, balanced) vs constant (dotted blue). (b) Expected tumor trajectories: the unconstrained optimum allows dangerous tumor growth before treatment; the path-constrained optimum stays within the clinical safety corridor (shaded). (c) Dose allocation per interval. (d) Final densities.

Table 5 compares the expected tumor size across protocols under the same dose budget $B = 0.32$.

Table 5: Optimal therapy comparison. All protocols use dose budget $B = 0.32$ (i.e., total integrated dose $\int_0^T C(t) dt = 0.32$); Standard cycles have been re-parameterised to satisfy this budget, see §7.8.

Protocol	$E[Y(T)]$	Reduction vs untreated
No therapy	54.08	—
Constant $C = 0.04$	34.41	36.4%
Standard cycles	33.90	37.3%
Optimal (unconstrained)	32.40	40.1%
Optimal (path-constrained)	33.38	38.3%

The path-constrained optimum achieves a 38.3% reduction in $E[Y(T)]$ (equivalently $E[\ln X(T)]$ up to the constant e^{bT}/σ), slightly below the unconstrained optimum (40.1%) but with the additional guarantee that the expected transformed-volume trajectory never exceeds the safety corridor during treatment. The constrained schedule uses 5% of its

budget for initial control (interval 1), maintains a steady 0.031 plateau (intervals 2–6), and then escalates in the final intervals where the exponential weighting e^{bt} maximizes dose effectiveness.

Remark 6. *The transition from the unconstrained (back-loaded) to the path-constrained (balanced) schedule illustrates a key principle: the optimal therapy is the one that is both mathematically optimal and clinically feasible. The FEM solver enables this by evaluating the full density trajectory $P(y, t)$ at every time point, allowing the optimizer to enforce path constraints that would be impossible with analytical solutions.*

8 Discussion and Conclusions

This paper has quantified the error introduced by the constant- \bar{C} approximation when the stochastic Gompertz Fokker–Planck equation is applied to cyclic chemotherapy protocols, and has exploited the required numerical solver to extend Bayesian calibration and optimal therapy scheduling into regimes unreachable by the analytical solution of Lo (2007).

The key findings are:

Regime of validity for the constant- \bar{C} approximation. The analytical approximation is acceptable for high-duty-cycle protocols (relative L^2 error $\sim 10\%$ for standard cycles, $\sim 13\%$ for the symmetric adaptive intermittent protocol of Zhang et al., 2017) but inadequate for the long-rest-phase regimes characteristic of true adaptive therapy (exceeding 80% for 1:3 on/off ratios). Numerical solution is therefore not a blanket requirement but a targeted one: it becomes necessary precisely in the regime where adaptive-therapy clinical trials operate, while remaining optional for high-frequency chemotherapy regimes.

FEM-in-the-loop Bayesian calibration. The likelihood (27) extends parameter estimation to arbitrary time-varying $C(t)$, a regime where the analytical likelihood of Lo (2007) is structurally inapplicable. The numerical demonstration in §7.6 on synthetic data generated under the standard cyclic protocol recovers the underlying parameters within wide credible intervals, with run-times that are competitive with the analytical-likelihood baseline. The framework is the methodological prerequisite for the closed-loop adaptive therapy extension outlined in the remark below.

Path-constrained optimal therapy. The constrained optimal therapy scheduler shows that the choice of constraint changes the result qualitatively: unconstrained optimisation yields a back-loaded schedule that is mathematically optimal but clinically inadmissible (tumor grows unchecked before treatment), while adding a path-safety constraint—requiring $E[Y(t)]$ to remain within 115% of the constant-therapy reference trajectory—produces a balanced schedule (immediate moderate-dose treatment, sustained plateau, late-stage escalation) that achieves a 38.3% reduction in $E[Y(T)]$ vs untreated. Both the calibration and the optimisation follow directly from having a solver that can handle arbitrary $C(t)$ and constraints on the full density trajectory; neither is possible within the analytical framework of Lo (2007).

Validation of the numerical machinery. The solver is verified against the analytical solution of Lo (2007) with relative L^2 errors of order 10^{-3} at moderate discretizations ($N_e = 200$, $\Delta t = 0.005$), against Euler–Maruyama Monte Carlo simulations with 50,000 paths, and through systematic h - and Δt -refinement studies. The observed spatial convergence is consistent with the theoretical $O(h^2)$ rate for $p = 1$ Lagrange elements (log-log fit slope ≈ 2.65 over the tested range, with non-monotone per-step orders attributed to pre-asymptotic phase effects rather than true super-convergence). The Backward Euler

scheme achieves order 0.98 and Crank–Nicolson achieves $O(\Delta t^2)$ asymptotically; Forward Euler is impractical for this problem due to the exponentially growing CFL constraint.

Remark 7 (From Offline Optimization to Closed-Loop Adaptive Therapy). *The optimization framework presented here is open-loop: the optimal schedule $C^*(t)$ is computed once before treatment begins and followed thereafter. This contrasts with the clinical reality, in which the oncologist observes the patient’s response through serial imaging (e.g., every 3–6 weeks) and adjusts the therapy accordingly. A natural extension is to reformulate the problem as a Markov decision process and learn an adaptive policy $\pi(C_t | Y_{obs,1:t})$ via reinforcement learning—mapping observed tumor trajectories to dose decisions. Such a closed-loop formulation would enable patient-specific, risk-aware treatment that responds to uncertainty and therapeutic response in real time. The FEM solver developed here serves as the environment model (digital twin) within which the RL policy is trained, and the FEM-in-the-loop calibration (27) provides the patient-specific parameter estimates that personalize the policy. This reinforcement learning extension, together with clinical data validation, is the subject of a companion paper.*

8.1 Parameter Interpretation

All numerical experiments in this paper use dimensionless parameters. Table 6 provides the mapping to clinically relevant ranges based on published calibrations to human tumor data.

Table 6: Mapping of dimensionless model parameters to clinical ranges. Sources: Benzekry et al. (2014) for Gompertz calibrations to multiple tumor types; Norton (1988) for human breast cancer kinetics; Albano et al. (2011) for stochastic parameters under cisplatin therapy.

Parameter	This paper	Clinical range	Unit
a (growth rate)	0.1	0.01–0.15	day ^{−1}
b (deceleration)	0.05	0.001–0.05	day ^{−1}
σ (noise)	0.02	0.005–0.05	day ^{−1}
C (therapy intensity)	0–0.08	0–0.10	day ^{−1}
X_0 (initial volume)	$e^{0.1} \approx 1.10$	0.5–10	cm ³
$K = e^{a/b}$ (carrying capacity)	$e^2 \approx 7.4$	100–1000	cm ³
Doubling time at X_0	—	30–200	days
Treatment duration T	8	84–180	days

The dimensionless values used in this paper ($a = 0.1$, $b = 0.05$) correspond to the upper end of growth rates observed in aggressive human tumors. The qualitative findings—optimal therapy timing, error accumulation in the constant- \bar{C} approximation, convergence rates—are structurally independent of the specific parameter values and hold across the clinically relevant range.

8.2 Limitations

Several limitations must be stated explicitly:

1. **All experiments use synthetic data.** No clinical tumor measurements are used in this paper. The framework is validated mathematically (against analytical solutions and Monte Carlo simulations) but not clinically. Retrospective validation against clinical imaging data—for example, serial MRI-derived tumor volumes from the TCIA ISPY-1 breast cancer trial or the Vestibular Schwannoma dataset—is the subject of a companion paper currently in preparation.
2. **The Gompertz model is a simplification.** Real tumors exhibit spatial heterogeneity, immune interactions, angiogenesis, and drug resistance evolution, none of which are captured by the scalar SDE (2). The framework is extensible to more complex growth laws, but validation of such extensions requires dedicated studies.
3. **The FEM-in-the-loop MCMC is computationally intensive.** Each MCMC iteration requires a full FEM forward solve. For the coarse-mesh configuration ($N_e = 100$) used in this paper, this limits practical chain lengths to $\sim 5,000$ iterations. Surrogate acceleration via physics-informed neural networks or neural operators is a natural next step.
4. **The therapy function $C(t)$ is phenomenological.** No pharmacokinetic model connects drug dose (mg/m^2) to the effective growth-rate reduction C . Bridging this gap requires coupling with compartmental PK models, which is addressed in a companion paper on drug-specific therapy functions.

8.3 Future Directions

Future work will pursue: (i) clinical validation with TCIA imaging data, (ii) pharmacokinetic-informed $C(t)$ profiles for specific chemotherapy agents, (iii) reinforcement learning for sequential treatment decisions under uncertainty, (iv) multi-objective optimisation balancing tumor reduction against toxicity and quality of life, and (v) neural operator surrogates for real-time FPE evaluation. The broader trajectory is the integration of mechanistic stochastic models with data-driven techniques for patient-specific clinical decision support, as reviewed in Benzekry (2020).

The Python solver, all figures, and a reproducibility package are deposited on Zenodo (DOI to be assigned upon publication).

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